

Presentation of project results
Additive manufacturing of large composite automotive components
(GINOP-2.1.7-15-2016-01968)
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The aim of the project was to develop an additive manufacturing technology for large composite automotive components in the spirit of weight reduction and circular economy.

The development of the project resulted in the development of an additive manufacturing technology system capable of additively manufacturing automotive components with complex geometries and superior mechanical properties.

Description of used patent for the prototype

The prototype is based on the patent "APPARATUS AND METHOD FOR PRODUCING A THREE-DIMENSIONAL OBJECT", PCT No: PCT/HU2016/000053. The inventor of the patent is Márton Bartos, one of the owners of i3D Technologies Kft. The PCT phase of the patent was funded under the GINOP project.

Background for the project idea and patent was that SLA devices can be classified into two typical layouts. The first is the so-called "bottom-up" layout, where the printed geometry is mounted on an upside-down slide carrier and lifted upwards out of the resin bath.

The second type of arrangement is the so-called 'top-down' arrangement, where the printed geometry is fixed from below to a slide table and immersed with it in a container filled with photopolymer or other light-solidifying material.

The disadvantage of the bottom-up approach is that it cannot sufficiently increase the speed of three-dimensional printing (additive manufacturing) compared to other known approaches.

In light of the known (top-down and bottom-up) solutions, there was a particular need to further increase the build speed of 3D printing (additive manufacturing) technologies in order to build 3D objects faster. This need is underpinned by the fact that speed is currently the most serious technological limitation of 3D printing methods (speed is the most frequent criticism by users).

The primary objective of the invention was to provide a device and method for producing a three-dimensional object that is as free as possible from the drawbacks of previously known approaches.

It was a further object of the invention to build a prototype and provide a method for producing a three-dimensional object that can achieve construction speeds for producing a three-dimensional object that exceed the construction speeds provided by known technologies.

The invention relates to an apparatus for the production of three-dimensional objects, comprising a radiation emitting arrangement capable of generating a growth radiation pattern, a container capable of receiving a building material which solidifies under the effect of irradiation by the growth radiation pattern, and a securing means adapted to support a building base dividing the container into a first support portion and a second support portion, the building base having a first growing side facing the first support portion and a second growing side facing the second support portion. The radiation emitting arrangement includes a first radiation emitting unit adapted to generate a first growth radiation pattern enabling the building base to grow from the first growth side, and a second radiation emitting unit adapted to generate a second growth radiation pattern enabling the building base to

grow from the second growth side. The invention further provides a method for producing a three-dimensional object.

Building the prototype

As a results of the R&D project using the above-mentioned patent for the additive manufacturing technology system is at 100% completion level.

The R&D project comprised of the following steps:

1. As a first step, the prototyping infrastructure and the design environment (workshop, tools, computer) were set up.
2. We then investigated the possibilities of reducing the surface tension of the photopolymer (photosensitive resin) used as a raw material for the fabrication and the resulting layer separation force. Examples of motion mechanisms were sought that could provide a satisfactory technical solution to the forces involved in the deposition process. The thermal and fluid dynamics aspects of the problem were approached empirically, the spatial dynamics of this viscous material were studied, and experiments were performed to find the time required for the photopolymer to travel a given distance in a given geometry of space. Among the mapped solutions, we have successfully identified the most advantageous version in terms of sustainability and additional technical parameters (optical and mechanical properties). Contact angle measurements were performed on the selected version and hydrophobicity boundary conditions were determined.
3. In the light of the above, the construction of the mechanical prototype model started, for which the following subtasks were carried out:
 - definition, dimensioning and design of main structural elements
 - mechanical and functional testing on an assembly model with pre-designed components
 - prototype construction and calibration
 - testing and transferring results that require changes to the prototype design
4. For the further development potential identified during the testing of the prototype model, the aim was to build a new prototype. The following steps were required:
 - reinforcement of the machine frame and the drive mechanism
 - redesign and production of parts affected by upgrades
 - assembly and functional testing
 - production optimisation and assembly design
 - finalisation of the construction
5. In parallel with the mechanical tasks, the control system responsible for the movement and timing of the various units and the printing process was also completed, which involved the following electrical engineering tasks:
 - setting up a system structure
 - setting up a development environment
 - circuit design and manufacture
 - testing
6. Once it was made sure that the engineering and controls were compatible, we the assembly of the complete system was carried out.

Results of the prototype tests

The system tests demonstrated that there are major differences in overall production time when the original and multi-directional 3D printing methods are compared. Final results show that printing speed can be increased by 60% using the multi-directional 3D printing method, while keeping the same level of dimensional accuracy.

The impact of the project on business

The prototype created during the project can be used as an intellectual product for the company: with the developed production technology the company can offer contract printing services, which will become a completely new activity in the company as a result of the project. With the prototype, the 3D printing activity can be carried out more competitively due to the technological innovations implemented in the project: the two-way printing process results in a significant reduction in the time needed to print an object. Thus, printing with this technology can be cheaper. The right to use the prototype itself can also be marketed (licensed), and opportunities are explored for this - either through manufacturing partnerships or for in-house production.

The company is considering the below as future development opportunities for the machine design:

- integration of post-printing and post-processing steps (post-polymerisation, material deconvolution) to further increase the speed of the production process.
- scaling up the projection area of the imaging unit responsible for illuminating the layers, which would also increase the size of the largest part that can be produced in one step.
- web-based processing software, which would increase the efficiency of print job preparation.

1. Attachment no.: Photo documentation for the project GINOP-2.1.7-15-2016-01968

Image 1: Finished prototype in closed condition

Image 2: Finished prototype with the door open

Image 3: Prototype workbench

Image 5: The prototype polymerisation chamber with open tank

Image 6: Polymerisation chamber of the prototype, with a sample placed on the centre plane

Image 7: The construction head with increased strength movement mechanism

Image 8: Prototype from the rear, with the control motor connected

Image 9: The prototype from the rear, with touchscreens and controls connected

